

EXERCISE BEHAVIORAL INTENTION AND CONTROL, AND THE PHYSICAL FITNESS OF THE MIDDLE-AGED WOMEN

Albert B. Araneta, MAEd, Darwin D. Ofrin, Ed.D.

College of Teacher Education-Graduate Studies and Applied Research, Laguna State Polytechnic University-San Pablo City Campus, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12705850>

ABSTRACT

Maintaining physical fitness requires exercise. As you get older, exercise and regular physical activity can help you stay healthy, strong, and independent. However, it is thought that middle-aged women engage in the least intense levels of physical activity and that these levels fall as they get older. By understanding how middle-aged women internalize behaviors, you can better comprehend their fitness objectives. It might shed light on the psychological and social elements that encourage or restrict their engagement in physical activity. This study examined the association between middle-aged women's physical fitness and their exercise behavioral intention and control in Barangay Castanas Sariaya, Quezon. In the study, the descriptive research approach was used together with surveys, observations, and questionnaires that were similar to those used in interviews. The middle-aged women were found to exercise in order to maintain their physical fitness and prevent health issues. Additionally, the respondents' physical fitness and internalization of the exercise activity are both partially maintained, along with their intention and control, both of which are partially maintained. However, they are very different in how they view the variables. It is advised that future researchers reproduce the study in another area and continue it by putting a physical fitness program into place depending on the requirements and responses of the respondents.

Keywords: *Exercise Behavioral Intention and Control, Physical Fitness, Middle-Aged Women.*

INTRODUCTION

Maintaining physical fitness requires regular exercise. Exercise and regular physical activity, according to Elmagd (2016), can keep you young-looking, active, and independent as you age. It helps people keep a healthy weight, build and maintain healthy bone density, muscle strength, and joint mobility, promote physiological well-being, lower their risk of surgery, and fortify their immune systems. Many people fall short of the recommended levels of physical activity despite these well-established advantages. Regular exercise is made more difficult by time and money constraints, physical and environmental restrictions, and demotivating influences like boredom and enjoyment. However, according to Stacey (2017), middle-aged women are thought to be the least physically active, and their intensity decreases with age. Research that is still in its early stages has shown that skeletal muscle's function as an endocrine organ mediates many of the advantages of exercise. That is, when muscles contract, several molecules are released that aid in tissue repair, the creation of new tissue, and several anti-inflammatory processes, all of which lower the chance of suffering a few inflammatory disorders.

According to Alexios (2020), a greater comprehension of middle-aged women's behavioral internalization is necessary to comprehend their exercise objectives. It might shed light on the psychosocial enablers and impediments to their engagement in any physical activities. This demonstrated that when compared to women outside of middle age, weight- and health-related goals are associated with more extrinsic and less intrinsic behavioral internalization.

According to McArthur (2017), in their middle years, almost half of women cut back on their regular activities. As they enter menopause, they simultaneously experience a decrease in basal metabolic rate and a loss of lean muscle. These women are more likely to gain weight and develop related co-morbidities as a result of the combined impacts. Petruzzello (2019) claimed that behavioral internalization and intention are the contents of goals for participating, whereas behavioral internalization represents the perceived locus of causality of the goal and intention is a critical factor in supporting sustained exercise, which in turn is associated with significant health outcomes. According to research by Molanoruzi, Khoo, and Morris (2015), sustained physical exercise depends heavily on intention. Global statistics reveal that only a small percentage of middle-aged and older people participate in the advised physical fitness activities. Further, the study by Rahman, Gu, and Akter (2020) has shown that lack of intention and internalization are the main reasons for this.

According to Wilson (2017), more women than men report exercising to reduce weight, shape their bodies, or enhance their looks. Women's absorption of sociocultural beauty standards may manifest itself in their physical activity goals relating to look and body form. Since this is not yet confirmed as true, further evidence is required to support it.

That's why the researcher of this study desires to determine the Exercise Behavioral Intention and Control, and the Physical Fitness of the Middle-Aged Women through assessing the relationship of the variables being used in the study.

Research Questions

This study attempts to determine the exercise behavioral intention and control, and the physical fitness of the middle-aged women in Brgy. Castañas Sariaya, Quezon.

Specifically, it aims to answer the following questions:

1. How do the respondents describe their intention in exercise in terms of:
 - 1.1 Personal attitude; and
 - 1.2 Social Norms?
2. How do the middle-aged women-respondents describe their behavioral internalization in terms of:
 - 2.1 External internalization;
 - 2.2 Introjected internalization;
 - 2.3 Identified internalization; and
 - 2.4 Integrated internalization?
3. How do the respondents describe their perceived behavioral control in exercise?
4. How do the respondents describe their physical fitness in terms of:
 - 4.1 Body Composition;
 - 4.2 Cardiovascular Endurance;
 - 4.3 Flexibility; and
 - 4.4 Muscular Strength?
5. Is there a significant relationship between intention to the physical fitness of the respondents?
6. Is there a significant relationship between perceived behavioral control to the physical fitness of the respondents?

METHODOLOGY

In this study, it employs the descriptive-correlational research methodology. In order to uncover fresh realities, this design concentrates on the current situation (Cruz, 2004). It makes methodical endeavors to define a topic, problem, phenomenon, service, or program, or it offers information or discusses viewpoints on a subject (Kumar, 2005). Descriptive research is a type of quantitative study that is used to define traits or functions and test particular hypotheses, according to Fluet (2020). It gathers information that is used to respond to a variety of what, when, and how inquiries regarding a specific population or group.

The respondents of the study are the middle-aged women in Brgy. Castañas Sariaya, Quezon. They are composed of one hundred twenty (120) middle-aged women from different Sitio's in Brgy. Castañas Sariaya, Quezon. They are purposively selected since the focus of the study is the middle-aged women in the age bracket of 40 to 60 years old.

In order to choose the participants for the study, purposive sampling was used. Purposive sampling is a term used in statistics to describe a class of non-probability sampling methods where units are chosen for the sample because they possess the qualities you are looking for. As a result, units are chosen "on purpose" in purposive sampling. This sampling technique, which is also known as "judgmental sampling, focuses on the researcher's judgment when identifying and choosing the people, cases, or events that can supply the most information to meet the study's objectives (Nikolopoulou, 2022). When a researcher wishes to speak with a specific group of people, he or she will utilize purposive sampling because all survey respondents are chosen because they meet certain criteria (Alchemer, 2021).

In this case, the researcher selects middle-aged women in Brgy. Castañas Sariaya, Quezon. It was consisted of one hundred twenty (120) middle-aged women from different Sitio's in Brgy. Castañas Sariaya, Quezon. They are chosen since the study focus on the middle-aged women in the age bracket of 40 to 60 years old.

The researcher employs the modified type of questionnaire (Corbin, Charles Lindsay, Ruth and Welk, Greg, 2019) to gather information on the exercise internalization, intention and control, and the physical fitness among the middle-aged women.

The questionnaire is written in English and translated in Tagalog so that the middle-aged women may easily understand the questions. The item in the questionnaire is rated into Likert-scale type. The content of the questionnaire is based on readings and reviews of related literature and studies. The questionnaire is divided into three main parts: (a) Behavioral Internalization, (b) Intention and Control, (c) and Fitness. The first part which is the behavioral internalization on exercise is composed of 20 statements which is divided in 4 sub-variables and each variable has 5 statements while intention and control on exercise is composed of another 15 statements which is divided in 3 sub-variables and each variable has 5 statements. The physical fitness on exercise is composed of 20 statements which are divided into 4 sub-variables and each variable has 5 statements.

The developed questionnaire is validated by consulting the research adviser for comments and suggestions. Then, it is presented to some experts for content critiquing. After incorporating the suggestions, it is again presented to his adviser. After the validation of the questionnaire, approval from the researcher's adviser is in need, to administer if the questionnaire is ready to distribute to the respondents.

To gather the data, permission is first sought from the respondents ensuring the preparedness of the instrument. Then, another letter of request is written for the approval of the presence of the respondents. After that the researcher formulated a questionnaire as the main instrument. The data that was gathered in this research study are from individual persons, the middle-aged women. Upon approval, the questionnaire is administered to the target respondents. The data was gathered facts, and principles served as a basis for drawing conclusions about the research problem. After gathering the answered questionnaires, these are statistically treated.

The collected data was tallied, tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted. To ascertain if there is a significant relationship between the exercise behavioral internalization, intention and control, and the physical fitness of the middle-aged women, the following statistical measures and tests were used to analyze the gathered data to answer specific problems of the study.

Mean and Standard Deviation was used to determine the behavioral internalization, intention and control, and the physical fitness of the middle-aged women.

Pearson Product-Moment Correlation was applied to determine if there is a significant relationship between behavioral internalization, intention and control, and the physical fitness of the respondents.

RESULTS

Table 1. Behavioral Internalization as to External Internalization

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I exercise because other people say I should. (Nag-eehersisyo ako dahil sinasabi ng ibang tao na ito ay dapat kong gawin.)	2.76	0.93	Agree
2. I exercise because a health professional advised me to. (Nag-eehersisyo ako dahil pinayuhan ako ng isang propesyonal sa kalusugan.)	3.16	0.77	Agree
3. I take part in exercise because my friends/ family/ spouse/ say I should. (Nakikibahagi ako sa ehersisyo dahil sinasabi ng aking mga kaibigan, pamilya, o asawa na ito ay dapat.)	3.03	0.75	Agree
4. I exercise because others will not be pleased with me if I don't. (Nag-eehersisyo ako dahil hindi matutuwa ang iba sa akin kung hindi ko ito gagawin.)	2.09	0.83	Disagree
5. I feel under pressure from my friends/family to exercise. (Nakararamdam ako ng <i>pressure</i> mula sa aking mga kaibigan o pamilya na mag-ehersisyo.)	2.18	0.73	Disagree
Over-all	2.64	0.91	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 2. Behavioral Internalization as to Introjected Internalization

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I feel guilty when I don't exercise. (Nakokonsensya ako kapag hindi ako nag-eehersisyo.)	2.41	0.87	Disagree
2. I feel like a failure when I haven't exercised in a while. (Nakararamdam ako ng pagkabigo kapag minsan akong hindi nag-eehersisyo.)	2.42	0.86	Disagree
3. I feel ashamed when I miss an exercise session. (Nahihiya ako kapag napalampas ko ang isang sesyon ng ehersisyo.)	2.35	0.86	Disagree
4. I feel a lack of energy if I don't exercise. (Nakararamdam ako ng panghihina kung hindi ako mag-eehersisyo.)	2.93	0.89	Agree
5. I feel upset if I don't exercise regularly. (Nababahala ako kapag hindi ako regular na nag-eehersisyo.)	2.73	0.77	Agree
Over-all	2.57	0.88	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 3. Behavioral Internalization as to Identified Internalization

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I get restless if I don't exercise regularly. (Hindi ako mapakali kapag hindi ako regular na nag-eehersisyo.)	2.53	0.81	Agree
2. I value the benefits of exercise. (Pinahahalagahan ko ang mga benepisyo mula sa pag-eehersisyo.)	3.43	0.64	Agree
3. It's important to make an effort to exercise regularly. (Mahalagang pagsumikapan ang pag-eehersisyo nang regular.)	3.37	0.65	Agree
4. It's important to me to exercise regularly. (Mahalaga sa akin ang pagkakaroon ng regular na pag-eehersisyo.)	3.33	0.70	Agree
5. I consider exercise a fundamental part of who I am. (Pag-eehersisyo ang itinuturing kong pangunahing bahagi kung sino ako.)	2.90	0.78	Agree
Over-all	3.11	0.80	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 4. Behavioral Internalization as to Integrated Internalization

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. I exercise because it's fun. (Nag-eehersisyo ako dahil ito ay masaya.)	3.23	0.72	Agree
2. I get pleasure and satisfaction from participating in exercise. (Nakakakuha ako ng kagalakan at kasiyahan mula sa pakikilahok sa pag-eehersisyo.)	3.30	0.64	Agree
3. I enjoy my exercise sessions. (Nalilibang ako sa bawat sesyon ng pag-eehersisyo.)	3.23	0.66	Agree
4. I find exercise a pleasurable activity. (Nakikita ko na ang pag-eehersisyo ay isang kasiya-siyang aktibidad.)	3.23	0.63	Agree
5. I will live longer if I exercise. (Mabubuhay ako nang matagal kung mag-eehersisyo ako.)	3.28	0.68	Agree
Over-all	3.26	0.66	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 5. Intention in Exercise as to Personal Attitude

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I want to improve my skills. (Nais kong pagbutihin ang aking mga kakayahan.)	3.48	0.56	Agree
2. Exercising makes me feel good. (Pag-eehersisyo ang nagpapasaya sa akin.)	2.93	0.73	Agree
3. I exercise for health concerns. (Nag-eehersisyo ako para sa aking pangkalusugan.)	3.48	0.58	Agree
4. I exercise to lose weight. (Nag-eehersisyo ako para mabawasan ang aking timbang.)	3.16	0.79	Agree
5. I exercise to give myself personal challenges to face. (Nag-eehersisyo ako upang bigyan ang aking sarili ng mga personal na hamon na haharapin.)	2.92	0.76	Agree
Over-all	3.20	0.73	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 6. Intention in Exercise as to Perceived Behavioral Control

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I'm getting older so exercise can be risky. (Tumatanda na ako kaya delikado na ang pag-eehersisyo.)	2.28	0.85	Agree
2. I'm just too tired after work to get any exercise. (Masyado lang akong pagod pagkatapos ng trabaho para makapag-ehersisyo pa.)	2.32	0.80	Disagree
3. I've been thinking about getting more exercise, but I just can't seem to get started. (Nag-iisip ako tungkol sa pagkuha ng higit pang ehersisyo, ngunit tila hindi ako makapagsimula.)	2.44	0.78	Disagree
4. I'm embarrassed about how I will look when I exercise with others. (Nahihiya ako sa magiging hitsura ko kapag nag-eehersisyo ako kasama ang iba.)	2.11	0.89	Disagree
5. Physical activity takes too much time away from other commitments- time, work, family, etc. (Ang pisikal na aktibidad ay tumatagal at kumukuha ng masyadong maraming oras mula sa iba pang mga aktibidad, oras, trabaho, pamilya, at iba pa.)	2.44	0.85	Disagree
Over-all	2.32	0.84	Disagree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 7. Intention in Exercise as to Social Norms

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. I like the social aspect of exercising. (Gusto ko ang sosyal na aspeto ng pag-eehersisyo.)	2.65	0.86	Agree
2. I like to meet new people. (Gusto kong makakilala ng mga bagong tao.)	3.03	0.82	Agree
3. I like to compare my abilities with other peoples'. (Gusto kong ihambing ang aking mga kakayahan sa ibang mga tao.)	2.43	0.88	Disagree
4. I like to show my importance to others. (Gusto kong ipakita ang aking kahalagahan sa iba.)	2.96	0.79	Agree
5. I like to show exercising with other people in the same age range is socially beneficial. (Gusto kong ipakita na ang pag-eehersisyo kasama ang ibang mga tao sa parehong hanay ng edad ay kapaki-pakinabang sa lipunan.)	3.08	0.71	Agree
Over-all	2.83	0.85	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 8. Physical Fitness as to Body Composition

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Through exercise my calories burn, and it helps me to stay fit. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo nasusunog nito ang aking mga calorie, at nakakatulong ito sa akin na manatiling fit.)	3.21	0.78	Agree
2. Through exercise I gain good body posture. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo nagkakaroon ako ng magandang postura ng katawan.)	3.30	0.69	Agree
3. Through exercise I can maintain my weight normal. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-eehersisyo, mapapanatili kong normal ang aking timbang.)	3.26	0.74	Agree
4. Through exercise my cholesterol levels in the blood keep lower. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-eehersisyo ang antas ng kolesterol sa aking dugo ay patuloy na bumababa.)	3.12	0.81	Agree
5. Through exercise I avoid getting symptoms of stroke. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-eehersisyo, naiiwasan kong magkaroon ng mga sintomas ng stroke.)	3.36	0.65	Agree
Over-all	3.25	0.74	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 9. Physical Fitness as to Cardiovascular Endurance

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Through exercise my stamina got strengthened. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo lumalakas ang aking stamina.)	3.36	0.62	Agree
2. Through exercise my diaphragm strengthens, and my intercostal muscles which helps me to increase my lung efficiencies. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ay lumalakas ang aking dayapragm, at ang aking mga intercostal na kalamnan na tumutulong sa akin na mapataas ang aking kahusayan sa baga.)	3.29	0.73	Agree
3. Through exercise my life span will be longer, and the risk of having a heart attack and congestive heart failure may lower. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ang buhay ko ay hahaba, at maaaring bumaba ang panganib na magkaroon ng atake sa puso at congestive heart failure.)	3.36	0.68	Agree

4. Through exercise my heart and lung health will improve. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ang kalusugan ng aking puso at бага ay bubuti.)	3.43	0.63	Agree
5. Through exercise the amount of oxygen that my blood can carry in the respiratory will increase. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ay tataas ang dami ng oxygen na madadala ng aking dugo sa respiratoryo.)	3.23	0.62	Agree
Over-all	3.34	0.66	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 10. Physical Fitness as to Flexibility

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
1. Through exercise I can avoid injuries and reduce the risk of getting fractures. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo maiiwasan ko ang pagkakaroon ng pinsala at mababawasan ang panganib na magkaroon ng bali.)	3.03	0.76	Agree
2. Through exercise the circulation of my blood improves, and my body becomes flexible. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ang sirkulasyon ng aking dugo ay bumubuti at nagiging flexible ang aking pangangatawan.)	3.34	0.67	Agree
3. Through exercise my level of joint mobilization improves. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ay bumubuti ang antas ng aking joint mobilization.)	3.23	0.64	Agree
4. Through exercise my muscles and joints can't go tighter. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ang aking mga kalamnan at kasukasuan ay hindi humihigpit.)	3.10	0.68	Agree
5. Through exercise my performance function increases and even coordination, while decreasing tension and stress. (Sa pamamagitan ng pag-eehersisyo ang aking pag-galaw o pagganap ay tumataas at maging ang koordinasyon, habang binabawasan ang tensyon at stress.)	3.23	0.63	Agree
Over-all	3.19	0.68	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 11. Physical Fitness as to Muscular Strength

Indicators	Mean	Std. Deviation	Verbal Interpretation
1. Through exercise my lean mass increases and strengthens my muscles. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ang aking lean mass ay tumataas at nagpapalakas ng aking mga kalamnan.)	3.16	0.65	Agree
2. Through exercise I don't lose strength as I get older. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo hindi ako nawawalan ng lakas habang tumatanda ako.)	3.24	0.62	Agree
3. Through exercise my balance and proprioception improve. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo bumuti ang aking balanse at proprioception.)	3.33	0.61	Agree
4. Through exercise I don't get tired easily in my daily work. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ay hindi ako madaling mapagod sa aking pang-araw-araw na gawain.)	3.22	0.66	Agree
5. Through exercise I preserve my muscle that I lose as I get older. (Sa pamamagitan ng ehersisyo ay napapanatili ko ang aking kalamnan na nawawala sa aking pagtanda.)	3.11	0.74	Agree
Over-all	3.21	0.66	Agree

Legend: 3.50 – 4.00 Strongly Agree; 2.50 – 3.49 Agree; 1.50 – 2.49 Disagree; 1.0 – 1.49 Strongly Disagree

Table 12. Relationship Between Internalization and Physical Fitness

Behavioral Internalization	Physical Fitness			
	Body Composition	Cardiovascular Endurance	Flexibility	Muscular Strength
External Internalization	0.212*	0.170	0.166	0.156
Introjected Internalization	0.286*	0.296*	0.266*	0.253*
Identified Internalization	0.343*	0.389*	0.350*	0.344*
Integrated Internalization	0.394*	0.376*	0.470*	0.428*

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Coefficients: .90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00) Very high positive (negative) correlation; .70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90) High positive (negative) correlation; .50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70) Moderate positive (negative) correlation; .30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50) Low positive (negative) correlation; and .00 to .30 (.00 to -.30) negligible correlation.

Table 13. Relationship Between Intentions and Physical Fitness

Intention	Physical Fitness			
	Body Composition	Cardiovascular Endurance	Flexibility	Muscular Strength
Personal Attitude Perceived	0.329*	0.390*	0.298*	0.343*
Behavioral Control	0.045	-0.008	0.052	-0.033
Social Norms	0.311*	0.232*	0.300*	0.237*

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed). Coefficients: .90 to 1.00 (-.90 to -1.00) Very high positive (negative) correlation; .70 to .90 (-.70 to -.90) High positive (negative) correlation; .50 to .70 (-.50 to -.70) Moderate positive (negative) correlation .30 to .50 (-.30 to -.50) Low positive (negative) correlation; and .00 to .30 (.00 to -.30) negligible correlation.

DISCUSSION

The data presented on Table 1 shows that indicator 2 (I exercise because a health professional advised me to) obtained the highest mean of 3.16 (SD=0.77) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 4 (I exercise because others will not be pleased with me if I don't) obtained the lowest mean of 2.09 (SD=0.83) with a verbal interpretation of Disagree. The overall mean was 2.64 (SD=0.91) interpreted as Agree. This suggested that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that external internalization influences the respondents' behavioral internalization in exercise. In their opinion, exercise is joyful and interesting and aids in their goal of remaining active and productive as they age. Additionally, as evidenced by their doctors' prescriptions, it is one of the activities that they most frequently recommend. That is why they attempt to continue exercising as part of their everyday routines even after finishing their tasks or jobs. Physical activity is subject to external regulation, according to (Campbell, Shaw, and Gilliom, 2000; Eisenberg et al., 2001). The term "externalizing behavior" or "external internalization problems" describes a collection of behavioral issues that show up in an adult's outward actions during exercise and reflect the adult's poor interactions with the outside world. These externalizing disorders are described in the research literature as having disruptive, hyperactive, and aggressive behaviors that occur mostly during physical activities or workouts (Hinshaw, 1987). You act in response to an external demand or in order to receive an external reward, which is known as external internalization. "Conduct problems," "antisocial," and "undercontrolled" as to their behavioral internalization are some phrases used to characterize externalizing behavior or external internalization issues (Hinshaw). Although the action is deliberate, a third party is in charge of it. This activity is then controlled from outside. An individual perceives an action that is subject to external influence as being under external pressure rather than being autonomous. The least desirable form of motivation, external internalization, is frequently used to contrast with intrinsic motivation.

On table 2, it shows that indicator 4 (I feel a lack of energy if I don't exercise) obtained the highest mean of 2.93 (SD=0.89) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other

hand, indicator 3 (I feel ashamed when I miss an exercise session) obtained the lowest mean of 2.35 (SD=0.86), with a verbal interpretation of Disagree. The over-all mean was 2.57 (SD=0.88) interpreted as Agree. This suggested that the respondents, middle-aged women, concurred that introjected internalization influences behavioral internalization in exercise. And according to the answers to the researcher's interview, exercise is the main source of their energy as they begin their daily lives, so when they don't exercise consistently, they feel low on energy and upset. They continue to exercise at least three times per week, despite the fact that it is difficult for them given their age, and they are not ashamed of it. (Thornton, 2020) asserts that introjected internalization (the urge to feel worthwhile, get other people's favor, or assuage guilt) is the driving force behind physical exercise. The human tendency to internalize other people's actions is known as introjection or introjected internalization. When someone does not want to stand out, usually when engaging in activities or exercises, it might be a protective strategy. In some situations, it is an attempt to be inclusive of a group. The mental process of assimilation through recurrent neural pathway reinforcement is known as introjected internalization. In other words, learning or exercising involves an internalization that is subconscious. According to Li (2022), this kind of internalization is still perceived as controlled because introjected behavior is carried out in response to internal pressure to lessen guilt or anxiety, bolster ego or pride, or maintain self-esteem or a feeling of self-worth, typically through engaging in physical activity or exercise. Even though the individual has accepted the activity's aim as required and its internal (psychological) intention, it is still not perceived as a "free choice." Because the behavior is not self-directed but rather controlled or coerced by internal conditions, introjected internalization is still not the desired sort of motivation.

The data presented on Table 3 indicator 2 (I value the benefits of exercise) gained the highest mean of 3.43 (SD=0.64) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 1 (I get restless if I don't exercise regularly) has the lowest mean of 2.53 (SD=0.81), with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The overall mean was 3.11 (SD=0.80) interpreted as Agree. This demonstrates that the respondents, who were women of middle age, concurred that respondents' behavioral internalization in exercise is most influenced by identified internalization. Physical activity, depending on the type of lifestyle, can strengthen bones and muscles, help people control their weight, lower their risk of disease, increase their capacity to carry out daily tasks, and improve their cognitive health. Adults who engage in any quantity of moderate-to-vigorous physical activity and sit less are said to get certain health benefits. Additionally, some individuals say that when they don't exercise frequently, they develop sleeplessness. According to (Ryan RM, 2004), even though the action is extrinsically motivated, it is still largely autonomous, and identified internalization may be a significant source of motivation for adults to engage in physical activity. recognized regulation (partially internalizing the results of physical exercise as being equivalent to one's own values and sense of self). Identified regulation refers to motivating one's actions or exercising for reasons that are personally significant to them.

Table 4 shows that indicator 2 (I get pleasure and satisfaction from participating in exercise) obtained the highest mean of 3.30 (SD=0.64) with a verbal interpretation of

Agree. On the other hand, three indicators, indicator 1 (I exercise because it's fun), indicator 3 (I enjoy my exercise sessions), and indicator 4 (I find exercise a pleasurable activity) obtained the lowest mean of 3.23 (SD=0.72), (SD=0.66), and (SD=0.63) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The over-all mean was 3.26 (SD=0.66) interpreted as Agree. This suggested that the respondents, who were middle-aged women, concurred that integrated internalization influences behavioral internalization in exercise. According to what they said throughout the interview, the majority of the respondents think that physical activity and exercise are nice and satisfying. You have the opportunity to relax, take in the outdoors, or simply do things that make you happy when you exercise. The act of physical activity has been fully merged into one's sense of self, which consists of one's fundamental personal values, beliefs, and purpose (Vallerand RJ, 2015). When a person has thoroughly absorbed the cause of an action, that is, studied the cause and determined that it is consistent with their own values and needs, integration has taken place. When it happens, the action starts on its own. It is usually in middle-aged women that it is autonomous and uncontrolled by outside motivators. Despite being extrinsic, integrated motivation has many of the same characteristics as intrinsic motivation. It is the ideal form of extrinsic motivation to use while engaging in any activities that contribute to an adult's physical fitness. Because the person has fully assimilated the extrinsic cause into their values, some researchers even refer to integrated internalization as intrinsic. Integrated internalization is the next best thing if intrinsic intention is not possible.

The data presented on Table 5 Indicator 3 (I exercise for health concerns) obtained the highest mean of 3.48 (SD=0.58) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 5 (I exercise to give myself personal challenges to face) obtained the lowest mean of 2.92 (SD=0.76) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The over-all mean was 3.20 (SD=0.73) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that personal attitude affects the respondents' intention in exercise. (Fishbein, 2017) asserts that people who are in good health typically have supportive views toward exercise. They view it as an essential component of their way of life and often plan regular times to engage in physical activity. Middle-aged adults can stay motivated and prevent overload and anxiety by maintaining a positive outlook on life. Finding ways to transform a bad attitude into a good one can help you perform at your best, even though it could involve time, work, and frequent maintenance. Having a positive outlook on life will help you achieve your goals in any activity if you're in your middle years. Please keep in mind that your energy level, as well as other parts of your physical performance, can be impacted by your emotions, both happy and sad. This includes your ability to think clearly.

Table 6 shows that indicator 5 (Physical activity takes too much time away from other commitments- time, work, family, etc), and Indicator 3 (I've been thinking about getting more exercise, but I just can't seem to get started) obtained the highest mean of 2.44 (SD=0.85), and (SD=0.78) with a verbal interpretation of Disagree. On the other hand, indicator 4 (I'm embarrassed about how I will look when I exercise with others) obtained the lowest mean of 2.11 (SD=0.89) with a verbal interpretation of Disagree. The over-all mean was 2.32 (SD=0.84) interpreted as Disagree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents disagreed that perceived behavioral control affects the respondents' intention in exercise. In his theory of planned behavior, (Ajzen, 2018) added the concept

of "perceived behavioral control" as a factor influencing both behavioral intention and actual action. Perceived behavioral control and self-efficacy are conceptually related. Both concepts refer to the person's sense of control over the behavior in question, but operationally, perceived behavioral control is frequently measured by how easy or difficult the behavior is, whereas self-efficacy is operationalized by the person's belief in their ability to carry out the behavior in the face of challenging situations. Perceived behavioral control has been included in (Schwarzer, 2009) as a significant predictor of desire to engage in a health behavior and/or as a predictor of engaging in the behavior.

On table 7, it shows that indicator 5 (I like to show exercising with other people in the same age range is socially beneficial) obtained the highest mean of 3.08 (SD=0.71) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 3 (I like to compare my abilities with other peoples') obtained the lowest mean of 2.43 (SD=0.88) with a verbal interpretation of Disagree. The overall mean was 2.83 (SD=0.85) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that social norms affect the respondents' intention in exercise. According to (Randazzo, 2016), social norms, which are defined as a person's perception of other people's conduct, offer a framework for examining the variables that affect whether or not a person chooses to engage in physical activity. Theoretically, social norms could have an impact on health-related behaviors like physical activity. However, empirical evidence linking social norms to these behaviors, apart from other social variables that are more frequently studied, including social support, is limited, and findings are ambiguous. This may be because of limitations in how social norms have been conceptualized and evaluated. After controlling for the effects of social support, this study examined relationships between clearly defined social norms and a variety of physical activities and behaviors among middle-aged women.

Table 8 shows that indicator 2 (Through exercise I gain a good body posture) obtained the highest mean of 3.30 (SD=0.69) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 4 (Through exercise my cholesterol levels in the blood keeps lower) obtained the lowest mean of 3.12 (SD=0.81) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The over-all mean was 3.25 (SD=0.74) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that exercise helps on their body composition. Body composition exercises, in accordance with (Patnaek, 2023), aid in achieving a fit and toned appearance. In order to achieve your ideal physique, it is crucial to understand your body composition (the proportion of muscle to fat on your body). If you are middle-aged, it is especially necessary to take this into account before engaging in any exercise. To change your body composition to have more muscle and less fat, or at least to maintain your muscular mass and lose the fat on top of your muscles, is what it means to "tone up" or seem more toned. It's your body's proportion of lean mass, or anything that isn't fat. Your overall weight includes your body composition, but it's important to understand your body composition rather than just your weight in order to determine how much of your body is made up of muscle and how much of it is fat.

On table 9, it shows that indicator 4 (Through exercise my heart and lung health will improve) obtained the highest mean of 3.43 (SD=0.63) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 5 (Through exercise the amount of oxygen that my

blood can carry in the respiratory will increase) obtained the lowest mean of 3.23 (SD=0.62) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The over-all mean was 3.34 (SD=0.66) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women agreed that exercise helps on their cardiovascular endurance. (Myers, 2022) defined cardiovascular exercise as any strenuous activity that boosts heart rate, breathing, oxygenation, and blood flow levels while utilizing a significant number of the body's big muscle groups in a rhythmic and repeating manner. Your cardiorespiratory fitness, commonly known as your CRF, tells a lot about your health and the likelihood of certain health outcomes. CRF assesses the efficiency with which your body absorbs oxygen and distributes it to your muscles and organs after extended activity. Exercise that uses a lot of the body's main muscle groups repeatedly and rhythmically is referred to as cardiovascular exercise. Cardiovascular exercise boosts heart rate, breathing, and oxygen and blood flow throughout the body. Your most important internal organs are gradually put to the test by this exercise, which also helps the heart, lungs, and circulatory system work more efficiently. Cardio helps a variety of health conditions, especially in middle-aged people, including heart health, mental health, mood, sleep, weight regulation, and metabolism.

Table 10 shows that indicator 2 (Through exercise the circulation of my blood improves, and my body becomes flexible) obtained the highest mean of 3.34 (SD=0.67) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 1 (Through exercise I can avoid injuries and reduces the risk of getting fractures) obtained the lowest mean of 3.03 (SD=0.76) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. The over-all mean was 3.19 (SD=0.68) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that exercise helps on their flexibility. According to (Hautier, 2020), flexibility training programs in middle-aged or older persons are frequently beneficial at enhancing joint range of motion in various joints, and many functional outcomes can be enhanced. However, older people are less focused on the high-performance advantages of enhanced flexibility and more concerned with being safely active and executing activities of daily living. Another typical reason for advising older people to participate in flexibility exercises is to prevent injury and falls. When paired with weight training, flexibility training may improve balance and postural stability. Because flexibility is the capacity of the muscles, joints, and soft tissues to move freely and painlessly, it involves these structures' unlimited flexibility, which enables effortless and effective movement. Adequate flexibility can improve performance in middle age, lower the risk of musculoskeletal ailments, and boost the general quality of life. Although everyone's ranges of flexibility differ significantly, they must be met in order to preserve the health of their joints and whole body. Genetics, age, degree of activity, and prior injuries are a few of the many factors that cause the loss of normal joint flexibility. The flexibility of the soft tissues around the joint, such as the muscles, ligaments, tendons, joint capsules, and skin, will have an impact on the range of motion. Lack of stretching, especially when coupled with exertion, might eventually cause soft tissue shortening brought on by tiredness.

Table 11 shows that indicator 3 (Through exercise my balance and proprioception improve) obtained the highest mean of 3.33 (SD=0.61) with a verbal interpretation of Agree. On the other hand, indicator 5 (Through exercise I preserve my muscle that I lose as I get older) obtained the lowest mean of 3.11 (SD=0.74) with a verbal interpretation of

Agree. The overall mean was 3.21 (SD=0.66) interpreted as Agree. This implied that the middle-aged women respondents agreed that exercise helps on their muscular strength. According to (Newman, 2019), muscle strength steadily declines from the 40th to roughly the 60th year of life. As they get older, the middle-aged need strength training more and more to maintain their mobility for daily tasks. Reducing muscle atrophy and the ensuing loss of motor function is the aim of training. Even at greater intensities, progressive strength training in the middle-ages is effective at preventing sarcopenia and maintaining motor function. The earlier age-related changes will show themselves; the less active a person's lifestyle is. The most notable of these changes is a decline in motor function as well as visual and vestibular abilities. A Pearson product-moment correlation was run to determine the relationship between internalization and physical fitness. External internalization has a very weak, positive correlation to cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.170$), flexibility ($p=0.166$), and muscular strength ($p=0.156$) which were both statistically not significant. On the other hand, external internalization has a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.212$) which was statistically significant. Introjected Internalization has a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.286$), cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.296$), flexibility ($p=0.266$), and muscular strength ($p=0.253$) which were all statistically significant. Identified internalization has a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.343$), cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.389$), flexibility ($p=0.350$), and muscular strength ($p=0.344$) which were all statistically significant. Integrated internalization has a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.394$), and cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.376$), while moderate positive correlation to flexibility ($p=0.470$), and muscular strength ($p=0.428$) which were all statistically significant.

Based on the data in Table 12, it is clear that even if the respondents are very busy with their daily responsibilities, they still value exercise and can find time to do it in order to maintain a healthy lifestyle, which becomes less important as they get older. According to the respondents, the importance of exercising frequently and feeling confident about it does not depend on whether they exercise alone or with others. And whether it comes before, during, or after their responsibilities and work, they enjoy exercising as part of their daily routine. According to interviews and surveys with respondents, the top three reasons people occasionally skip workouts are a lack of inspiration, a lack of resources, and a lack of time. However, as of right now, thanks to the researcher's assistance, these problems do not have to keep individuals from getting in shape, becoming healthy, and understanding all the benefits exercise can have on their lives. (Ryan & Deci, 2000) assert that there is a strong connection between internalization and physical health. According to their self-determination theory, behavioral internalization in middle-aged women may account for variations in motivation and physical fitness performance. Additionally, the internalization of the exercise behavior would have a favourable effect on an individual's intention, physical fitness, and level of physical activity. Internalization of self-regulated behavioral patterns can positively predict the intention to engage in physical activity. Personal attitude has a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.329$), cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.390$), flexibility ($p=0.298$), and muscular strength ($p=0.343$) which were all statistically significant. Perceived behavioral control has a very weak, negative correlation to cardiovascular endurance ($p=-0.008$) and muscular strength

($p=-0.033$) which were both statistically not significant. Likewise, perceived behavioral control has a very weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.045$) and flexibility ($p=0.052$) which were both statistically not significant as well. Social norms have a weak, positive correlation to body composition ($p=0.311$), cardiovascular endurance ($p=0.232$), flexibility ($p=0.300$), and muscular strength ($p=0.237$) which were all statistically significant.

Table 13 shows a limited correlation between respondents' physical fitness and their personal attitudes and social norms under intention. One of the key reasons people engage in an activity, particularly when it comes to fitness, is their personal attitude, according to the respondents. It piques their curiosity and inspires them to engage in workouts on their own or with others. They develop self-confidence, muscles, and social skills with others their own age or within a range of ages with the aid of exercise. They can express themselves through exercise, which relieves tension and allows them to forget about issues that might otherwise result in illnesses or problems. In their opinion, the reasons why some middle-aged people don't exercise are because they are too exhausted from their jobs, lack desire, or lack time. However, with the help of peers and professionals, some middle-aged people's opinions about exercising have changed. And according to some respondents who are now employed, exercise boosts worker productivity by boosting blood flow to the brain and facilitating concentration. Additionally, it encourages original thought, assisting staff in coming up with unique answers to challenging issues. According to (Teixeira, 2012), there is a consistent correlation between intention and physical fitness that favors more autonomous forms of intention, with identified internalization tending to predict initial or short-term adoption more strongly than intrinsic intention and intrinsic intention favoring long-term exercise adherence. Across a variety of groups and contexts, exercise engagement is positively predicted by competence satisfaction and higher intrinsic intention, according to some studies. There was conflicting evidence about the function of different kinds of intention (such as personal attitude, perceived behavioral control, and social standards), as well as the unique characteristics and outcomes of introjected internalization.

Conclusions

The findings gathered in the study led to the formulation of the conclusion: (1) It was found out that there was insignificant and significant relationship existed between among the variables of intention and to the physical fitness of the respondents, then the null hypothesis is partially sustained. (2) Since there was insignificant and significant relationship existed between among the variables of perceived behavioral control and to the physical fitness of the respondents, then the null hypothesis is partially sustained.

Recommendations

Based on the results and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are hereby suggested: (1) To the Middle-Aged Women, they would gain knowledge about the importance and benefits of having regular exercises making them gain self-improvement reducing exercise barriers. Result would guide them on how to gain a healthy lifestyle

that can lead to preventing chronic diseases, and to manage their behavioral regulation and motives to engage in different types of activity or exercises, that they can use and share to those people who mostly needed the physical activities. (2) To the community, it would lessen the growing population of inactive people in physical fitness activities. It would also help them to lower the continuous growing number of people with disease. Also, this study would also arouse the interest of the community, the people themselves and the planner to be aware of the process and means of improving health. (3) For the local health officers, they can use the result of the study as springboard in knowing the reasons and lifestyle of the middle-aged adults to their community. That way, they can provide some answers and solutions to the problem of their middle-aged people so they can motivate them to engage in some activities where they can be productive. (4) To the future researchers, this study can guide them to do a thesis about knowing the behavioral internalization, intention of an individual about the exercise and it can help them conduct an effective program. This research would give them knowledge about the consequences and profit of exercise and physical fitness activities. It can motivate future researchers to produce another study which will be concerned to the internalization and importance of having a good healthy lifestyle for the middle-aged women.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The authors declare compliance in ethical standard. All respondents gave their informed consent for inclusion before they participated in the study. Their anonymity has been observed as well. No conflict or harm has been done in gathering data. Proper citation of related literature and studies are maintained. More importantly, there is no bias or prejudice in the findings and results of this study.

Acknowledgments

The researcher is very grateful to God Almighty for the wisdom, strength, courage, and good health bestowed upon him to accomplish his research. Immeasurable appreciation and deepest gratitude for guidance and support are extended to the family and Laguna State Polytechnic University San Pablo City Campus who contributed to making this study possible.

REFERENCES

- Ajzen, I. (2018), "The theory of planned behavior," *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 179–211.
- Elmagd, M. A. (2016). Benefits, need for and importance of daily exercise. ~ 22 ~ *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports, and Health*.
- McArthur D. and Stacey D. (2017). Factors influencing adherence to regular exercise in middle-aged women: A qualitative study to inform clinical practice. *BMC Women's Health*.
- Molanoruzi, K. et al., (2015), "Motives for adult participation in physical activity: type of activity, age, and gender," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 15, no. 1, p. 66.

- Rahman, M. et al., (2020). Effects of Attitude, Intention, and Eagerness for Physical Activity among Middle-Aged and Older Adults. *Journal of Healthcare Engineering*.
- Randazzo, K(2016), "How do Social Norms Affect Physical Activity and Performance on an Endurance Task?". LSU Doctoral Dissertations.1594.https://digitalcommons.lsu.edu/gradschool_dissertations/1594
- Ryan, R. M. (2004), "The "what" and "why" of goal pursuits: human needs and the self-determination of behavior," *Psychological Inquiry*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 227–268.
- Thornton, A. (2020). *Principles for Physical Fitness Profile Plus for Health*. Wadsworth City, USA: Wadsworth Publishing Company.
- Vallerand, R. (2015), "An integrative analysis of intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in sport," *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 142–169.
- Wilson, P. (2017). The Relationship between Exercise Intention and Physical Self-Esteem in Female Exercise Participants: An Application of Self-Determination Theory 1. *Applied Biobehavioral Research* 7 (1) 30-43.